

2 Poems by Dr.Ezhil Vendhan

SKYLARK

Genus of bird I am
perch not in trees or bushes
but flying down from heaven,
identified by the long descending whistle,
undulating dive-bombing flight.

I forage on the earth for my foodstuff
crouch and take to shuttle
roost at dawn alighting on the ground.

My song flight soaring up
with tweets its unique,
diving with slightly closing my wings,
and then rising up in a glide.

My undulating flight hang out
by a long whistle at each dive
and at the tip of each rise
by a sharp chirpy note.

I descend at an angle and landing,
on mounds trying to reach out you
only for your rejoinder
and flying high again
after waiting for a moment.

Thunders, lightning, rain
quaker, tsunami and on and on
are mundane for me,
nothing could annoy or exasperate me.

I'm longing to witness from the clouds
nothing but unadulterated breeze,
serene natural water, the boon of planet earth,
hills and forests ever green
animals of all kind moving around
care free without fear .

I have no language but
other than universal tweets
welcoming love, peace
and spring all the while.

I presumably trust in you,
infinitesimal I am understood.

I fly high as I sing
and I sing as I fly high.

AN INTERCEDE

You claim to be pious and spiritual
You preach high morals
You speak of faith and harmony
You pronounce peace and love for all.

You assert yourself for truth
You proclaim to be noble
But why do you scare others
Who are weak and marginalized
Who are underprivileged and poor
Who are in hunger and poverty.

What is your meaning for love?
Whether you have love without concern
Don't you love for the wellness of all.
Does goodness to others is not your meaning of love.

How you like to translate your love
Is there any other interpretation for your love.
Why you propagate hatred and enormity
Why are you dishonest to your own claims.

And then what you stand for
I intercede for love and peace.
Compose yourself of the best
as this life is precious and you only live once
make out maximum sweetness you can
to the life and lessen the bitterness.

Bio:

Dr. Ezhil Vendhan is a celebrated poet from India and a recipient of numerous international accolades and author of four poetry collectios in English and Tamil two in each languages. And his first poetry collection LUMINOUS TENTACLES has been translated and published in Indian languages Assamese and Odia and Chinese, Russian, French and Azerbaijani translations by eminent poets are under print.

He has been honoured with the ‘World Laureate in Literature 2017’ by the World Nations Writers’ Union, Kazakhstan and ‘World Icon of Peace’ by World Institute of Peace, Nigeria for his contribution to the world literature. The ‘Fellow of the Regal World of Scribes’ and ‘Enchanting Muse’ have been conferred on him by the Writers Corner International during the World Poetry Festival in October 2017.

He can be contacted by email address: dr.ezhilvendan@gmail.com.